

AWARENESS OF GLOBAL WARMING AMONG PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS

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Abstract:

Nowadays global warming is considered as a burning problem and it is being a challenge to the entire world and its scientific society. Global warming is a worldwide environmental problem by which there is an abnormal increase to the level of temperature, particularly in a natural environment. Lack of awareness on effect of the global warming is an essential problem. This problem should be solved by the future teachers at some extent by increasing the level of awareness, in this way the study is considered as needful one. The main objective of the study to identify the level of awareness on global warming among student-teachers who are undergoing training at colleges of education. For this a sample of 294 was collected from the respondents who are working in various colleges. T-test was used as tool to analyse the data. The conclusion is that there is a significant relationship between gender, educational qualification and awareness of global warming among prospective teachers. While taking decision on and awareness of global warming among prospective teachers their gender and educational qualification has to be taken for decision making process.

Key Words: Global Warming, Environment & Temperature

Introduction:

Global warming and climate change are terms for the observed century-scale rise in the average temperature of the Earth's climate system and its related effects. Multiple lines of scientific evidence show that the climate system is warming. Although the increase of near-surface atmospheric temperature is the measure of global warming often reported in the popular press, most of the additional energy stored in the climate system since 1970 has gone into ocean warming. The remainder has melted ice and warmed the continents and atmosphere. Many of the observed changes since the 1950s are unprecedented over tens to thousands of years. When the greenhouse gases can't escape the earth's atmosphere global warming can be possible but only some amount is distributed to outer space. After that the extra greenhouse gases could increase the earth's temperature. Consequently, the both the poles lose. Generally, it causes melting of ice and all our coasts have heavy rain fall or more rain.

Statement of the Problem:

Lack of awareness on effect of the global warming is an essential problem. This problem should be solved by the future teachers at some extent by increasing the level of awareness, in this way the study is considered as needful one. Little knowledge on an environmental problems and global warming will affect the student-teachers and society to suffer a lot. Particularly by increasing the knowledge about global warming may help the society and students to know how to survive. . By knowing about global warming, they can have a better survival in near future. In this way the study has its own importance.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To identify the level of awareness on global warming among student-teachers who are undergoing training at colleges of education.
- ✓ To identify the level of awareness among student-teachers in each and every aspect of global warming.
- ✓ To identify the significant difference if any between the different groups of biographical variables such as location of the college, sex and subjects in global warming.
- ✓ To suggest some practical solution to reduce or to avoid the dangerous effect of global warming.

Hypotheses:

H01: There is no significant relationship between Gender and awareness of global warming among prospective teachers

H02: There is no significant relationship between educational qualification and factors related to awareness of global warming among prospective teachers

H03: There is no significant relationship between group and factors related to awareness of global warming among prospective teachers

H04: There is no significant relationship between location of the school and awareness of global warming among prospective teachers

Research Questions:

- ✓ Significant relationship between Gender and awareness of global warming among prospective teachers?

- ✓ Relationship between educational qualification and factors related to awareness of global warming among prospective teachers?
- ✓ Relationship between group and factors related to awareness of global warming among prospective teachers?
- ✓ Relationship between location of the school and awareness of global warming among prospective teachers?

Limitations of the Study:

The study has certain limitation, which are as follows:-

- ✓ Only 294 college lecturers are selected as sampling for this study.
- ✓ The project has been restricted to analysis and studies in awareness of global warming among prospective teachers.
- ✓ The study is restricted to the college lecturers of Coimbatore.
- ✓ The study is restricted to the few colleges in Coimbatore.
- ✓ Study is conducted using only one tool.

Methodology:

Design of the Study: In the presence study “Normative” survey method will be adopted. Survey research employee questioner and interview to our people who provide information’s about them self’s their attitude and believes demographic(Age, gender, income and so on) the survey method can be classified into many, but according to the objectives and hypotheses in this presence study normative survey method will be adopted.

Sample of the Study: The sample for the investigation consisted of 294 college lecturers.

Tools Used for the Study: T-test

Analysis and Interpretation:

H01: There will be significant mean score difference in awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on gender (Male / Female)

Table 1: Mean score difference and t-value of factors related to Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on gender

		N	Mean	S D	Df	t-value	P value	Result
Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on gender	Male	150	1.2164	.02892	292	2.121	0.035	S
	Female	144	1.2078	.04010				
	Total	294	1.2122	.03505				

Interpretation:

The table 1 shows the mean score difference in Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on gender (male / female). The calculated t-value is statistically not significance at 0.05 levels and hence the hypothesis 1 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in mean score difference in awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on gender.

H02: There will be significant mean score difference in Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on educational qualification (UG / PG)

Table 2: Mean score difference and t-value of factors related to Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on educational qualification

		N	Mean	S D	Df	t-value	P value	Result
Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on educational qualification	UG	182	1.2075	.03690	293	-2.972	0.003	S
	PG	112	1.2198	.03046				
	Total	294	1.2122	.03505				

Interpretation:

The table 2 shows the mean score difference in Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on educational qualification (UG / PG). The calculated t-value is statistically not significance at 0.05 levels and hence the hypothesis 1 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in mean score difference in awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on educational qualification.

H03: There will be significant mean score difference in Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on group (science / arts)

Table 3: Mean score difference and t-value of factors related to Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on group

		N	Mean	S D	Df	t-value	P value	Result
Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on group	Science	223	1.2132	.03665	293	.912	0.363	NS
	Arts	71	1.2089	.02945				

	Total	294	1.2122	.03505				
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Interpretation:

The table 3 shows the mean score difference in Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on group (science/arts). The calculated t-value is statistically not significant at 0.05 levels and hence the hypothesis 3 is accepted. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference in mean score difference in Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on group studying of the respondents.

H04: There will be significant mean score difference in Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on location of the school (rural / urban)

Table 4: Mean score difference and t-value of factors related to Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on location of the school

		N	Mean	S D	Df	t-value	P value	Result
Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on location of the school	Rural	150	1.2063	.03998	293	-2.990	0.003	NS
	Urban	144	1.2183	.02789				
	Total	294	1.2122	.03505				

Interpretation:

The table 4 shows the mean score difference in Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on location of the school (rural / urban). The calculated t-value is statistically not significant at 0.05 levels and hence the hypothesis 4 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in mean score difference in Awareness of global warming among prospective teachers based on location of the school.

Findings:

The collected data were analyzed using T-test to test the hypothesis formulated for the study. The following are the major findings and results of the present study.

- ✓ There is a significant relationship between Gender and factors related to awareness of global warming among prospective teachers.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between educational qualification and awareness of global warming among prospective teachers.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between group and factors related to group and awareness of global warming among prospective teachers.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between location of the school and factors related to awareness of global warming among prospective teachers.

Summary of the Findings:

A study on awareness of global warming among prospective teachers was studied and the findings reveal that there is no significant difference between awareness of global warming among prospective teachers and gender, educational qualification and location of school.

Educational Implications:

Students themselves need to have a clear understanding of the global warming issues in relation to other factors such as the impact of biotechnology on the environment before they can act as effective changing agents within the larger society.

Theoretical aspects of environmental awareness strategies on global warming can be introduced as a unit of core subjects in the graduate Teacher Training curriculum.

The practical inputs regarding environmental awareness strategy should be taken up through subject specific programmes such as lesson plan writing, observation classes and practice teaching.

Preventive Measures on Global Warming:

“Prevention is better than cure”. To prevent the Global Warming the following steps should be taken care.

- ✓ Emphasis on decentralized industries.
- ✓ Encouragement for free forming or afforestation.
- ✓ Preservation and management of forest.
- ✓ Water management.
- ✓ Dusting the nature by using appropriate technology.
- ✓ By using 3Rs approach as Reduce, Reuse and Recycle, the problem may be minimized.
- ✓ Resource utilization as per carrying capacity.
- ✓ Developing awareness on environment education may reduce all the problem related to earth and its atmosphere.
- ✓ Developing a life style on harmony with nature.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that there is a significant relationship between gender, educational qualification and awareness of global warming among prospective teachers. While taking decision on and awareness of global

warming among prospective teachers their gender and educational qualification has to be taken for decision making process.

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